

Spatio-temporal Fluctuations of Water-sided Gas Concentration Fields under Wind-induced Turbulence

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Fluctuations of concentration fields of dissolved gases close to the water surface have thoroughly been examined in grid or jet stirred tanks (e.g., Tsumori et al., 2007, Herlina et al., 2008, Schulz et al., 2009, Asher et al., 2009). Under purely wind-induced turbulence, however, experimental investigations are rare. Münsterer et al., 1998, studied merely mean vertical concentration profiles and gas transfer rates. Only Walker et al., 2008 investigated wind-induced turbulence in combination with mechanically generated waves.

In this work, high-resolution measurements of water-sided gas concentration fields are presented under the condition of purely wind-induced turbulence, therefore with focus on the mechanisms of air-sea gas exchange. Measurements were performed using planar laser-induced fluorescence (PLIF) with plane orientation normal to the surface and parallel to the wind-direction in combination with an acid tracer gas (HCl) as Münsterer et al. [1998], with three significant improvements:

Firstly, the fluorescent pH-indicator 8-Hydroxypyrene-1,3,6-trisulfonic acid trisodium salt (HPTS) is used instead of fluorescein. HPTS offers a larger Stokes shift (53 nm versus 25 nm of fluorescein) and a higher photo-stability than fluorescein [Falkenroth et al., 2006]. Secondly, the optical resolution is improved. Aberrations are minimized by using the camera in a Scheimpflug arrangement. Thirdly, the intensity of the vertical light-sheet is varied randomly in horizontal direction (Fig. 1). These patterns are used to determine the along-wind slope of the short wind waves and to correct for intensity variations resulting from lens effects caused by the water surface. Figure 1 indicates that these distortions are not significant close to the water interface with distances up to ten times the thickness of the thin mass boundary layer. However, LIF data gained at greater depth has to be corrected for these described distortion effects to avoid wrong gas concentration reconstruction.

Image sequences with 67 frames per second and a resolution of 1400 x 1024 pixels were acquired at fetches from 0.4 to 2.0 m in a linear wind-wave facility and wind speeds up to 8 m/s. Currently, a detailed analysis of the images is underway. Image analysis is used to a) detect the water surface and to extract the wave height (Fig. 3) and b) to correct for the horizontal intensity fluctuations. The result is a remapped concentration field in a coordinate system attached to the water surface (Fig. 2). At the symposium we will show a detailed analysis of a) the spatio-temporal variations of the thickness of the mass boundary layer (and thus the instantaneous local gas transfer rate) and b) the frequency and type of surface renewal events.

Figure 1:
Raw LIF image of an injection-event at a wind speed of 5 m/s blowing from right to left and 1.6 m fetch. The total imaged area is 35 x 26 mm, pixel resolution 25 micrometer; the segmented water surface is marked with white-dashed line. The distorted image above the water surface is caused by total reflection at the wavy water surface.

Figure 2:
Rectified LIF image computed from Figure 1 with the water surface at the top of the image and corrected for horizontal intensity fluctuations

Figure 3:
Wave Height extracted from LIF-image in Figure 1

References

- Asher W. E., Litchendorf T.: Visualizing near-surface turbulence concentration fluctuations using laser-induced fluorescence, *Exp. Fluids*, 46, 243-253, 2009.
- Falkenroth A., Herzog A., Jähne B.: Visualization of air water gas exchange using novel fluorescent dyes, *12th Int. Symposium on Flow Visualization, 10-14 Sept., Göttingen, 2006*
- Herlina, Jirka G. H.: Experiments on gas transfer at the air-water interface induced by oscillating grid turbulence, *J. Fluid Mechanics*, 594 : 183-20, 2008.
- Münsterer T., Jähne B.: LIF measurements of concentration profiles in the aqueous mass boundary layer, *Exp. Fluids*, 25, 190-196, 1998.
- Schulz H. E., Janzen J. G.: Concentration fields near air-water interfaces during interfacial mass transport: oxygen transport and random square wave analysis, *Braz. J. Chem. Eng.*, 26(3), 527-536, 2009.
- Tsumori H., Sugihara Y.: Length scales of motions that control air-water gas transfer in grid-stirred turbulence, *J. Marine Systems*, 66, 6-18, 2007.
- Walker J. W., Peirson W. L.: Measurement of gas transfer across wind-forced wavy air-water interfaces using laser-induced fluorescence, *Exp. Fluids*, 44(2), 249-259, 2008